

THE IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS AND VOCABULARY LEARNING STRATEGIES IN TO THE LANGUAGE ANXIETY OF THE BSED COLLEGE STUDENTS

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The Impact of Communication Skills and Vocabulary Learning Strategies in to the Language Anxiety of the BSED College Students

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the impact of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies in to the language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in a local college in Davao del Norte. The study is quantitative research that utilizes a descriptive-correlational approach and regression analysis. A sample of 266 randomly selected Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students who were identified using stratified random sampling answered the surveys on the three variables. Results showed that the level of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies were both high in level, while the level of language anxiety was moderate. Results also revealed that there was a significant relationship between communication skills and language anxiety. Likewise, there was also a significant relationship between vocabulary learning strategies and language anxiety of the students. Moreover, results show that all domains of communication skills such as competence, discouragement, body language, and dignification can significantly influence communication skills. Finally, it was revealed that domains of vocabulary learning strategies such as metacognitive strategy, determination strategy, and social strategy can significantly predict language anxiety of the respondents. Results implied that the variables were significant in predicting the language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students. It implies that teachers should provide a supportive environment where students can share resources, ask questions, and discuss language learning challenges can foster collaboration and reduce anxiety. They should also examine the different learning styles of the learners to help them enhance their language learning. Teachers should provide accessible resources and support mechanisms to help students enhance their communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies while effectively managing language anxiety.

Keywords: *communication skills, vocabulary learning strategies, language anxiety, BSED students, Philippines*

Introduction

Language anxiety is a phenomenon that can affect individuals who are learning a new language. This debilitating experience often manifests as fear, apprehension, and self-doubt when communicating in the target language. It is rooted within themselves, fear of making linguistic mistakes and facing social scrutiny, language anxiety can have significant implications for learners' confidence and overall linguistic development, hindering effective communication and impeding language learning that leads to poor performance (Jugo, 2020).

In India, English is an important language for communication, and many people feel pressured to speak it well because it's necessary for good jobs and career advancement. This pressure had caused language anxiety among students, especially when it comes to speaking English. When students struggle to speak English confidently, it made them even more anxious feel even more anxious, lose confidence, and may avoid joining conversations or discussions, which had negative impact their learning (Mehdi et al., 2019).

In the Philippines, most Filipinos dedicate their school time to learning English, as mandated by the government. Consequently, English serves as the primary teaching language in several higher education institutions in the Philippines. Despite its widespread use, a significant number of Filipinos, including college students, still feel uneasy when using English for communication, and this leads to the emergence of language anxiety that hinder them to communicate effectively specifically in the presence of others. The findings indicated that a significant factor contributing to language anxiety are limited language proficiency, self-doubt, fear of criticism, and external negative influences can hinder learners' performance. (Giray et al., 2022).

Considering these factors, it's important to conduct a study that focuses on the emergences of language anxiety within the leaners specifically among BSED College students considering the communication skills, and vocabulary learning strategies. This study is quite urgent to conduct because it was a concerning common phenomenon that can affect the learners' educational performance. If neglected it leads to reduction of self-esteem, and can hinder the language learning of the learners, impeding effective communication and limit academic progress of the students which can potentially affect their overall learning performances and professional opportunities. Moreover, it was socially relevant as it could leads to a deeper understanding of the connection between communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies, paving way for important information that offered strategies and perspectives regarding language anxiety among students, particularly in the locality where the study was conducted. Therefore, the dissemination of the results could benefit other researchers, professional practitioners, and the wider community to alleviate and reduce the language anxiety of the students.

There were several studies that had been conducted in related research endeavors such as the study by Liu et al., (2021) entitled, "English Language Classroom Anxiety and Enjoyment in Chinese Young Learners" revealed that many participants, regardless of

gender or grade, experienced anxiety while speaking English, but over half felt joy in their English class. Moreover, the conducted research by Alamer and Almulhim (2021), titled "The Interrelation Between Language Anxiety and Self-Determined Motivation: A Mixed Methods Approach," closely examined the different types of anxieties students faced while learning a language and analyzed how motivational factors, grounded in self-determination theory, could predict these specific anxieties. However, no further research has been conducted on the factors contributing to language anxiety, particularly the influence of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies on students. To address this gap, acknowledged the necessity of carrying out a study that examines the impact of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies on the language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students, specifically at the local college in Kapalong, Davao del Norte.

Finally, the findings will be disseminated through publishing the study in reputable academic journals focused on language learning and student well-being. Also, the results will be presented at local and regional educational conferences to share insights and gather feedback from peers. Consequently, by combining publication in a peer-reviewed journal with presentations at academic conferences, the researcher aimed to reach a broad audience of educators and researchers, helping to address the problems discussed and implement the suggested recommendations.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine the significant relationship between communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies in to the language anxiety of the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST). To be specific, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of communication skills of students in terms of:
 - 1.1. competence;
 - 1.2. discouragement;
 - 1.3. body language; and
 - 1.4. dignification
2. To determine the level of vocabulary learning strategies of students in terms of:
 - 2.1. memory strategy;
 - 2.2. cognitive strategy;
 - 2.3. metacognitive strategy;
 - 2.4. determination strategy; and
 - 2.5. social strategy;
3. To determine the level of language anxiety of students in terms of:
 - 3.1. communication apprehension;
 - 3.2. test anxiety; and
 - 3.3. fear of negative evaluation
4. To determine the relationship between;
 - 4.1. communication skills and language anxiety; and
 - 4.2. vocabulary learning strategies and language anxiety
5. To determine which domain/s of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies that can considerably influence the language anxiety of the students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study was quantitative, as it quantified the problem by generating numerical data or data that could be converted into usable statistics. Quantitative research was defined as a method for testing objective ideas by examining the relationships between variables. These variables could be measured using instruments, and the resulting numerical data could be analyzed through statistical methods and structured approaches such as surveys. Statistical data is typically collected in the form of numerical data and analyzed to draw conclusions that inform the final course of action (Apuke, 2017).

In the context of this study, the quantitative approach was chosen to systematically investigate and measure the problem at hand. By generating numerical data, the research aimed to offer a clear and objective understanding of the relationships between communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies in relation to the language anxiety experienced by the respondents. The use of quantitative methods allowed the researchers to collect data that could be statistically analyzed, offering precise insights and patterns that might not be evident through qualitative methods alone. Instruments such as surveys were employed to gather this numerical data, ensuring a structured and replicable approach to data collection.

Additionally, the researcher utilized a descriptive quantitative research design, specifically utilizing a descriptive-correlational research technique. The focus of descriptive-correlational research method is on describing relationships among variables without aiming to establish a causal link. This approach identifies patterns and associations between variables, using statistical methods to analyze data.

While providing valuable insights, this method cannot prove causality, as there may be unaccounted variables or factors at play (Quaranta, 2017).

In the context of the study, the study employed a descriptive-correlational research design, focusing on three primary variables: communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies as independent variables, and language anxiety as the dependent variable. The participants in the study were students enrolled in the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) program. This approach aimed to describe the current state of these variables and examine the correlations between them, providing insights into how communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies influenced language anxiety levels among the students. The findings could inform educational strategies to mitigate language anxiety in this population.

Furthermore, this study employed regression analysis, a statistical method used to examine the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. It sought to represent the dependent variable as a function of the independent variables, allowing researchers to estimate the value of the dependent variable based on the independent variables. Hence, it helped to evaluate the strength of these relationships and can be used to predict future interactions. This method is valuable for understanding and modeling how variables influence each other (Taylor, 2015).

In the context of the study, Regression analysis was employed to investigate the relationship between communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies as the independent variables, with language anxiety as the dependent variable. By representing language anxiety as a function of these independent variables, the regression analysis allowed researchers to examine how communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies influence levels of language anxiety, highlighting their impact on student well-being and academic performance. This approach underscored the importance of using regression analysis to unravel the complex interactions between communication skills, vocabulary learning strategies, and language anxiety, guiding targeted interventions and educational practices aimed at supporting students' holistic development.

Respondents

This study involved BSED college students enrolled in Academic Year 2023-2024 at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST) of Barangay Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. The respondents in the study were primarily drawn from this institution using the Slovin's formula. The respondents of the study were 266 samples out of the population of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students from the first year and second year levels during the first semester of A.Y. 2022-2023. The respondents were based on these inclusion criteria: they were 18 years old and above; male or female; and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students from the first year and second year levels of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. The students who were selected as respondents were chosen since the focus of the study was on the impact of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies on the language anxiety of the students, making it fitting and valid to include the BSED students.

On the other hand, the exclusion criteria for the study included BSED students who were under 18 years old, as they did not meet the age requirement. Students from the third year and above, as well as those not enrolled in the first semester of A.Y. 2022-2023, were excluded to maintain consistency in the study population. Additionally, students from other colleges or programs at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology, or those not enrolled in the BSED program, were excluded to ensure the study's focus remained on BSED students. Consequently, a stratified random sampling approach was employed to ensure randomness and preserve the study's element.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

Respondents	Population	Sample	Percentage
BSED (First Year & Second Year)			
English	359	120	15.15%
Filipino	266	89	11.22%
Mathematics	169	57	7.13%
TOTAL	794	266	33.50%

The researcher utilized the stratified sampling method to select participants of the study. This approach involved dividing a larger population into smaller groups based on specific characteristics relevant to the study. Rather than randomly selecting from the entire population, samples are chosen from each of these categories. This method improves sample representativeness by ensuring proportional representation of each subgroup, leading to more accurate and generalizable results. The choice of stratified random sampling sought to address the research goals and minimize potential bias in participant selection (Hayes, 2023).

In this study, stratified random sampling was used to select participants from the first year and second year level of Bachelor of Secondary Education, ensuring representation from the year level. Information about the population was collected from the Office Registrar by first writing a letter for the collection of data. After gathering, the data was sent to a statistician who calculated the study sample, allowing for a more accurate representation of the population by proportionally including each group.

The table displayed information regarding the distribution of respondents among various academic years with Bachelor of Secondary

Education (BSED) English from first year and second year level, 11.22% of BSED-Filipino from first year and second year level, and 7.13% of BSED-Mathematics from first year and second year level. The sample size for this dataset is 266, consisting of 120 BSED-English from first year and second level, 89 BSED-Filipino from first year and second level, and 57 BSED-Mathematics from first year and second level.

Instrument

The researcher utilized adapted questionnaires from web sources to measure the variables. These adapted questionnaires used in the study underwent thorough validation process before dissemination of the research questionnaires to the respondents. The researcher utilized the instruments for Communication Skills based on the study of Akkuzu and Akkaya (2014) which consisted of 4 indicators such as competence, discouragement, body language, and dignification with 36 statement items. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the factors "competence," "discouragement," "body language," and "dignification" were computed at 0.87, 0.83, 0.74, and 0.70, respectively. Additionally, the overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the entire scale was determined to be 0.89, indicating high reliability and homogeneity among the scale items.

While, the second set of questionnaires was based on Schmitt's (1997) taxonomy of VLS and adapted from Cheung (2004) which consisted of the following indicators such as memory strategy, cognitive strategy, metacognitive strategy, determination strategy, and social strategy with 33 statements. This instrument indicated that there were four cognitive strategy statements, eleven memory strategy statements, six metacognitive strategy statements, three social strategy statements, and nine consolidation strategy statements. The survey questionnaire demonstrated acceptable internal consistency, as indicated by a Cronbach's alpha of 0.893, ensuring the reliability of the instrument used in the study.

The third and last set of questions is the dependent variable of the study language anxiety, was based on the study of Horwitz et al. (1986) that is a 5-point Likert scale with a following indicators: communication apprehension; test anxiety; and fear of negative evaluation with 18 statements. The results indicated that communication apprehension had the highest mean score at 3.41, while test anxiety had the lowest mean score among the three primary factors at 3.33, with fear of negative evaluation obtaining a mean score of 3.39. Results showed that the 0.90 internal consistency of Cronbach's alpha meeting the excellent reliability level.

Moreover, the Likert scale is a five-point measurement tool, allows individuals to show how much they agree or disagree with a statement. It provides options for responses, allowing participants to express the strength of their agreement or feelings about the statement (McLeod, 2023). In this research, the five-point Likert scale used to evaluate participants' communication skills, vocabulary learning strategies, and language anxiety levels.

The scale was employed to assess agreement or disagreement with statements regarding the influence of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies on language anxiety among learners. This scale facilitated data collection that could be analyzed to determine the impact of these factors on language anxiety. Respondents utilized the scale by selecting a numerical response, ranging from 'always' to 'rarely,' corresponding to their agreement level with each statement. Scores across items were then totaled to provide participants with an overall score. Additionally, the questionnaire's overall effectiveness was evaluated through consolidation of feedback and assessments from expert validators, ensuring its reliability and suitability for the study.

Procedure

The following steps were done to collect the data for this study.

Questionnaire Formulation and Development. The researcher searched the questionnaires from reputable journal articles and related internet research which were positively related to the three variables.

Revision and Validation of Questionnaires. Afterwards, it was submitted to the panel of experts to be evaluated and contextualized. Upon receiving feedbacks and corrections, the researcher followed the advice of those revision experts until it would be approved for administration.

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher first made a permission letter that addresses to the College President of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. After the permission was approved by the College President, the researcher explained and made the BSED college students who were my respondents informed of the procedure of conducting the study, after getting their approval from the given written consent.

Distribution of Questionnaires. Upon receiving the approval of the College President, the researcher distributed the research instruments to the respondents with the help of the resource students of this study.

Collection and Tabulation of Data. At this point, the research instruments were collected after the students completely answering it, and was gathered together to tabulate the data gathered.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in computation of the data as well as the testing of the hypothesis at alpha 0.05 level of significance.

Mean. This used to determine the levels of language anxiety, communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies.

Pearson-r. This statistical tool was used to determine the significant relationship between the language anxiety, communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies.

Regression. This was used to determine the significant impact of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies on the language anxiety of the respondents.

Ethical Considerations

To guarantee the appropriate execution of this research and the well-being of all individuals participating in this study, I adhered rigorously to the highest ethical considerations. These considerations ensured the participants' safety, rights and trust in the researcher, and the purpose of the study were given appropriate action and justice. These ethical considerations are the following: informed consent, risk of harm, anonymity and confidentiality, and conflict of interest (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Informed Consent. The respondents were fully aware of the nature of the study, the intended use of their data, and any potential consequences. To participate, they need to give informed permission, acknowledging their right to access their data and the option to withdraw at any time. The informed consent process serves, to some extent, as a legal agreement between the researcher and participants (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this study, respondents were presented with an informed consent form prior to engagement. During the processes, the respondents were first oriented about the study's purpose, benefits, risks, and funding, allowing them to make an informed decision to participate or decline.

Risk of Harm, Anonymity and Confidentiality. It ensures that respondents' personal information, such as names and identifying details, remains confidential throughout the study, safeguarding participants against potential harm or adverse outcomes. Anonymity also helps prevent biases, as researchers are not influenced by participants' personal characteristics. Maintaining participant anonymity often involves using codes or pseudonyms instead of actual names and implementing measures to secure the confidentiality of any collected personal information (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, strict measures were taken to protect the security and privacy of the collected data. Personal details like names and addresses were carefully taken out to keep the data anonymous and clean. The researcher would securely keep all the data during the study. After the completion of the study, the data will be responsibly destroyed in line with the rules, three years after that. This careful process underscores the commitment to maintaining information confidentiality and following ethical rules when managing and storing data.

When publishing sensitive data, there was a risk of causing social harm, so the study's data was kept secure and confidential to prevent such incidents. The researcher took care to protect the personal data of respondents to address this concern. Survey questions did not ask respondents to provide personal information such as their name, email, or contact number.

Conflict of Interest. It pertains to instances where personal considerations, such as financial interests, could potentially compromise an investigator's professional judgment in conducting or reporting research. Conflicts of interest in research, whether stemming from existing relationships or prior actions, should be transparently disclosed during the ethical approval process. This allows the committee to provide guidance on managing these conflicts, ensuring that personal interests or commitments do not compromise the study's integrity. Conflicts may involve financial or nonfinancial benefits and can impact a researcher's impartiality, undermining confidence in results (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this study, as the researcher and respondents shared the role of students, there was no conflict of interest. However, conflicts would raise if the researcher has the ability to coerce participation through pressure or authority, such as blackmail, benefit termination, or punishment. For instance, a student-researcher in the same institution could create a conflict of interest by using authority or influence to pressure peers into participating, potentially promising rewards or threatening social consequences for non-compliance. Therefore, it was crucial for the researcher to avoid any conflict of interest, including financial interests, ensuring the integrity of the studies in which they were involved.

Results and Discussion

In the section below, discussions and findings were presented concerning the data on communication skills, vocabulary learning strategies, and language anxiety of BSED students. The chapter presents the data on the following: the communication skills; the level of vocabulary learning strategies; the level of language anxiety; the individual significant relationship of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies on language anxiety; and the significant influence of the domains of communication skills and vocabulary learning strategies that can possibly predict language anxiety.

Level of Communication Skills in Terms of Competence

The level of communication skills of BSED students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, competence.

The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 is the level of communication skills of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of competence. The data revealed that the level of communication skills in terms of competence had a total mean of 3.32 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicated that the level of communication skills of BSED students in terms of competence is sometimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.48 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 3 –Trusting myself when I make a speech.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 3.21 and have a moderate level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is sometimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 4 – Believing that I speak in a certain order and logic.

Table 2. *Level of Communication Skills of Students in terms of Competence*

Competence	Mean	Description
Feeling confident when I make a presentation in front of community.	3.37	Moderate
Trusting myself when I make a speech.	3.48	High
Expressing my feelings and thoughts clearly in front of community.	3.28	Moderate
Believing that I speak in a certain order and logic.	3.21	Moderate
Speaking fluently during communication.	3.25	Moderate
OVERALL	3.32	Moderate

Level of Communication Skills in Terms of Discouragement

The level of communication skills of BSED students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, discouragement. The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 3 is the level of communication skills of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of discouragement. The data revealed that the level of social literacy in terms of social skills had a total mean of 4.12 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of social literacy of BSED- English students in terms of social skills is oftentimes manifested.

Table 3. *Level of Communication Skills of Students in terms of Discouragement*

Discouragement	Mean	Description
Behaving naturally during speech.	3.70	High
Choosing words carefully during speech.	3.89	High
Communicating my thoughts and feelings to people.	3.74	High
Using necessary words while talking.	3.75	High
Being calm when encountering negative thoughts.	3.66	High
OVERALL	3.75	High

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.89 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 2 – Choosing words carefully during speech.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 3.66 and have a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 5 – Being calm when encountering negative thoughts.

Level of Communication Skills in Terms of Body Language

The level of communication skills of BSED students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, body language. The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 4 is the level of communication skills of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of body language. The data revealed that the level of communication skills in terms of body language had a total mean of 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent of high.

This indicated that the level of communication skills of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of body language is oftentimes manifested.

Table 4. *Level of Communication Skills of Students in terms of Body Language*

Body Language	Mean	Description
Using fillers while listening to someone.	3.57	High
Keeping the eye contact while listening to someone.	4.09	High
Showing my approval by nodding.	4.00	High
Using body language during speech.	3.95	High
Wanting my listeners to listen while I am speaking.	4.32	Very High
OVERALL	3.99	High

The highest mean among the survey items is 4.32 which indicates a very high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5 – Wanting my listeners to listen while I am speaking.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 3.57 and have a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 1 – Using fillers while listening to someone.

Level of Communication Skills in Terms of Dignification

The level of communication skills of BSED students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, dignification. The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 5 is the level of communication skills of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of dignification. The data revealed that the level of communication skills in terms of dignification had a total mean of 4.04 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of communication skills of BSED students in terms of dignification is oftentimes manifested.

Table 5. *Level of Communication Skills of Students in terms of Dignification*

Dignification	Mean	Description
Preferring dialogues rather than monologues.	3.61	High
Being open to criticism while speaking.	3.81	High
Wanting people to respect my ideas.	4.25	High
Being good listener because I perceive what is said accurately and completely.	4.23	High
Understanding the situation that someone is in while she/he is speaking.	4.29	High
OVERALL	4.04	High

The highest mean score among the survey items is 4.29 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5 – Understanding the situation that someone is in while she/he is speaking.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.61 and have a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 1 – Preferring dialogues rather than monologues.

Summary of the Level of Communication Skills

Presented in Table 6 is the overall level of communication skills of BSED students in terms of competence, discouragement, body language, and dignification. The data revealed that the level of communication skills of BSED students has a total mean of 3.77 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that communication skills is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents.

Table 6. *Level of Communication Skills of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Students*

Indicators	Mean	Description
Competence	3.32	Moderate
Discouragement	3.75	High
Body Language	3.99	High
Dignification	4.04	High
OVERALL	3.77	High

Further, the highest mean is 4.04 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of communication skills in terms of dignification is oftentimes manifested.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is competence which obtained a mean of 3.32 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the level of communication skills in terms of dignification is sometimes manifested.

Additionally, discouragement obtained a mean of 3.75 which means high. This indicates that the level of communication skills in terms of discouragement is oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, body language obtained a mean of 3.99 which means high. This indicates that the level of communication skills in terms of body language is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Vocabulary Learning Strategies in Terms of Memory Strategy

The level of vocabulary learning strategies of BSED students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator memory strategy. The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 7 is the level of vocabulary learning strategy of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of memory strategy. The data revealed that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of memory strategy had a total mean of 3.73 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of vocabulary learning strategies of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of memory strategy is oftentimes manifested.

Table 7. *Level of Vocabulary Learning Strategy of Students in terms of Memory Strategy*

Memory Strategy	Mean	Description
Linking the word to a visual image in my mind.	3.86	High
Linking the word to another English word with a similar sound.	3.61	High
Remembering the sentence in which the word is used.	3.75	High
Making up my own sentences using the new word.	3.63	High
Trying to use newly learned words in imaginary situations in my mind.	3.80	High
OVERALL		High

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.86 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – Linking the word to a visual image in my mind.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 3.61 and have a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 2 – Linking the word to another English word with a similar sound.

Level of Vocabulary Learning Strategies in Terms of Cognitive Strategy

The level of vocabulary learning strategies of BSED students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator cognitive strategy. The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 8 is level of vocabulary learning strategies of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of cognitive strategy. The data revealed that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of cognitive strategy had a total mean of 3.82 with a descriptive equivalent of high.

This indicated that the level of vocabulary learning strategies of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of cognitive strategy is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 4.03 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – Saying the word repeatedly in my mind.

Table 8. *level of Vocabulary Learning Strategies of Students in terms of Cognitive Strategy*

Cognitive Strategy	Mean	Description
Saying the word repeatedly in my mind.	4.03	High
Spelling the word repeatedly in my mind.	3.89	High
Saying the word aloud repeatedly.	3.71	High
Writing the word repeatedly.	3.62	High
Analyzing the part of speech of the new word.	3.85	High
OVERALL	3.82	High

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 3.62 and have a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 4 – Writing the word repeatedly.

Levels of Vocabulary Learning Strategies in Terms of Metacognitive Strategy

The level of vocabulary learning strategies of BSED- English students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator metacognitive strategy. The responses of BSED- English students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 9 is the level of vocabulary learning strategies of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of metacognitive strategy. The data revealed that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of metacognitive strategy had a total mean of 3.60 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of vocabulary learning strategies of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of metacognitive strategy is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.83 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 1 –Engaging actively with the target language by reading, watching films, listening to radio, and communicating with native speakers.

Table 9. *Level of Vocabulary Learning Strategies of Students in terms of Metacognitive Strategy*

Metacognitive Strategy	Mean	Description
Engaging actively with the target language by reading, watching films, listening to radio, and communicating with native speakers.	3.83	High
Getting myself a vocabulary test.		
Working and practicing vocabulary with peers in groups.	3.52	High
Setting a specific time for vocabulary learning.	3.45	Moderate
Setting priorities about which words are essential, not so important, not important at all, and to what extent (passive, active).	3.51	High
	3.70	High
OVERALL	3.60	High

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 3.45 and have a moderate level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is sometimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 3 – Working and practicing vocabulary with peers in groups.

Levels of Vocabulary Learning Strategies in Terms of Determination Strategy

The level of vocabulary learning strategies of BSED students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator determination strategy. The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 10 is the level of vocabulary learning strategies of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of determination strategy. The data revealed that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of determination strategy had a total mean of 3.67 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of vocabulary learning strategies of level of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of determination strategy is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.91 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5- Using dictionary to check the words.

Table 10. *Level of Vocabulary Learning Strategies of Students in terms of Determination Strategy*

Determination Strategy	Mean	Description
Analyzing the word by breaking it into sound segments.	3.53	High
Analyzing the affixes and roots of the new word.	3.58	High
Checking for the native language meaning of new.	3.68	High
Analyzing any available pictures or gestures to guess.	3.67	High
Using a dictionary to check the words.	3.91	High
OVERALL	3.67	High

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 3.53 and have a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 1 – Analyzing the word by breaking it into sound segments.

Level of Vocabulary Learning Strategies in Terms of Social Strategy

The level of vocabulary learning strategies of BSED students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator social strategy. The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 11 is the level of vocabulary learning strategies of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of social strategy. The data revealed that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of social strategy had a total mean of 3.42 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate.

This indicated that the level of vocabulary learning strategies of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of social strategy students is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.95 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 5 – Feeling more comfortable seeking clarification from classmates about unfamiliar words.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 3.25 which indicates a moderate level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is sometimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 1 – Asking the teacher for the new words to paraphrase.

Table 11. *Level of Vocabulary Learning Strategies of Students in terms of Social Strategy*

Social Strategy	Mean	Description
Asking the teacher for the new words to paraphrase	3.25	Moderate
Asking the teacher, the translation of the new words.	3.30	Moderate
Asking classmates for the meaning of the word.	3.47	Moderate
Engaging actively in group activities to grasp the meanings of new words.	3.49	Moderate
Feeling more comfortable seeking clarification from classmates about unfamiliar words.	3.59	High
OVERALL	3.42	Moderate

Summary of the Level of Vocabulary Learning Strategies

Presented in Table 12 is the overall level of vocabulary learning strategies of BSED students in terms of memory strategy, cognitive strategy, metacognitive strategy, determination strategy, and social strategy. The data revealed that the level of vocabulary learning strategies of BSED students has a total mean of 3.65 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that vocabulary learning strategies is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents.

Further, the highest mean is 3.82 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of cognitive strategy is oftentimes manifested.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is social strategy which obtained a mean of 3.42 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of social strategy is sometimes manifested.

Additionally, memory strategy obtained a mean of 3.73 which means high. This indicates that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of memory strategy is oftentimes manifested.

Moreover, metacognitive strategy obtained a mean of 3.60 which means high. This indicates that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of metacognitive strategy is oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, determination strategy obtained a mean of 3.76 which means high. This indicates that the level of vocabulary learning strategies in terms of determination strategy is oftentimes manifested.

Table 12. *Level of Vocabulary Learning Strategies of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Students*

Indicators	Mean	Description
Memory Strategy	3.73	High
Cognitive Strategy	3.82	High
Metacognitive Strategy	3.60	High
Determination Strategy	3.67	High
Social Strategy	3.42	Moderate
OVERALL	3.65	High

Level of Language Anxiety in Terms of Communication Apprehension

The level of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator communication apprehension. The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 13 level of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of communication apprehension. The data reveal that the level of language anxiety in terms of communication apprehension had a total mean of 3.17 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicated that the level of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of communication apprehension is sometimes manifested.

The highest mean is 3.28 which indicates a moderate level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item is sometimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – Being sure of myself when I am speaking in English in classroom. In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.09 and have a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This means that the item and the statement is sometimes manifested. This is from item no. 5 – Feeling comfortable around native speakers of the English language.

Table 13. *Level of Language Anxiety of Students in terms of Communication Apprehension*

Communication Apprehension	Mean	Description
Being sure of myself when I am speaking in English in classroom.	3.28	Moderate
Feeling confident when I speak English in classroom.	3.17	Moderate
Feeling not conscious in self when speaking the second language in front of other students.	3.21	Moderate
Being not tense and nervous when speaking English.	3.10	Moderate
Feeling comfortable around native speakers of the English language.	3.09	Moderate
OVERALL	3.17	Moderate

Level of Language Anxiety in Terms of Test Anxiety

The level of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator test anxiety. The responses of BSED students on each indicator were presented and analyzed above.

Presented in Table 14 is the level of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of test anxiety. The data revealed that the level of language anxiety in terms of anxiety had a total mean of 3.34 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicated that the level of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of test anxiety is sometimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.61 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 4 – Striving to excel by putting effort into classroom preparation. In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 3.03 and have a moderate level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is sometimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 3 – Feeling excited when I'm about to be called in classroom.

Table 14. *Level of Language Anxiety of Students in terms of Test Anxiety*

Test Anxiety	Mean	Description
• Feeling confident if I am well prepared to speak English language in classroom.	3.60	High
• Having motivation to speak English in my classroom because I don't get anxious easily.	3.26	Moderate
• Feeling excited when I'm about to be called in classroom.	3.03	Moderate
• Striving to excel by putting effort into classroom preparation.	3.61	High
• Staying calm and confident about upcoming English language tests	3.22	Moderate
OVERALL	3.34	Moderate

Level of Language Anxiety in Terms of Fear of Negative Evaluation

The level of language anxiety of BSED students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator fear of negative

evaluation. The responses of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 15 is the level of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of fear of negative evaluation. The data revealed that the level of language anxiety in terms of fear of negative evaluation had a total mean of 3.11 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicated that the level of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students in terms of fear of negative evaluation is sometimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.63 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is always manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – Being okay if I happen to make mistake while using English language in classroom.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey is 2.73 and have a moderate level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the item and the statement is sometimes manifested by the respondents. This is from the item no. 3 – Thinking that I am better at speaking English language than other students.

Table 15. *Level of Language Anxiety of Bachelor of Students in terms of Fear of Negative Evaluation*

Fear of Negative Evaluation	Mean	Description
Being okay if I happen to make mistake while using English language in classroom.	3.63	High
Finding myself being confident towards my proficiency in English language.	3.22	Moderate
Thinking that I am better at speaking English language than other students.	2.73	Moderate
Being confident when I have to speak without preparation in classroom.	2.96	Moderate
Feeling confident to volunteer answering in any classroom.	3.01	Moderate
OVERALL	3.11	Moderate

Summary of the Level of Language Anxiety

Presented in Table 16 is the overall level of language anxiety of BSED students in terms of communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation. The data revealed that the level of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students has a total mean score of 3.84 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that language anxiety is sometimes manifested as perceived by the respondents.

Further, the highest indicator is test anxiety which obtained a mean of 3.34 with the descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the level of language anxiety in terms of test anxiety is sometimes manifested.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is fear of negative evaluation which obtained a mean of 3.11 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the level of language anxiety in terms of fear of negative evaluation is sometimes manifested by the respondents.

Lastly, communication apprehension obtained a mean of 3.17 which means moderate. This indicates that the level of language anxiety in terms of communication apprehension is sometimes manifested.

Table 16. *Level of Language Anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Students*

Indicators	Mean	Description
Communication Apprehension	3.17	Moderate
Test Anxiety	3.34	Moderate
Fear of Negative Evaluation	3.11	Moderate
OVERALL	3.21	Moderate

Significant Relationship Between Communication Skills and Language Anxiety

The data revealed that the level of communication skills of BSED students have a total mean score of 3.77 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the communication skills is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents. On the other hand, the data also revealed that the level of language anxiety of BSED students have a total mean score of 3.21 with the descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the language anxiety is sometimes manifested as perceived by the respondents. The result

of the significant relationship between communication skills and language anxiety were presented below.

Presented in Table 17 is the result of the significant relationship between communication skills and language anxiety with an R-value of .536. In this study, 53% of language anxiety is attributed to the influence of communication skills, while the remaining 47% is due to unexplored variables. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected within this context. This impose that there is a positive, moderate, and significant relationship between communication skills and language anxiety.

Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, this means that there is a significant relationship between communication skills and language anxiety. This further explains the two variables simultaneously increases or decreases together, without giving any data on which one of the variables causes the increase or decrease of either variable.

Table 17. *Significant Relationship Between Social Literacy and Communication Skills*

Variables Correlated	Mean	r-value	p-value	Decision @=0.05
Communication Skills	3.77	.536	<.001	H₀ Rejected
Language Anxiety	3.21			

Significant Relationship Between Vocabulary Learning Strategies and Language Anxiety

The findings revealed that the level of vocabulary learning strategies of BSED students have a total mean score of 3.65 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the vocabulary learning strategies is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents. On the other hand, the findings also revealed that the level of language anxiety of BSED students have a total mean score of 3.21 with the descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the language anxiety is sometimes manifested as perceived by the respondents. The result of the significant relationship between communication skills and language anxiety were presented below.

Presented in Table 18 is the result of the significant relationship between communication skills and language anxiety with an R-value of .509. In this study, 51% of language anxiety is attributed to the influence of vocabulary learning strategies, while the remaining 49% is due to unexplored variables. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected within this context. This impose that there is a positive, moderate, and significant relationship between vocabulary learning strategies and language anxiety.

Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, this means that vocabulary learning strategies can influence the language anxiety of the BSED students. This further explains the two variables simultaneously increases or decreases together, without giving any data on which one of the variables causes the increase or decrease of either variable.

Table 18. *Significant Relationship Between Vocabulary Learning Strategies and Language Anxiety*

Variables Correlated	Mean	r-value	p-value	Decision @=0.05
Vocabulary Learning Strategies	3.65	.509	<.001	H₀ Rejected
Language Anxiety	3.21			

Significant Influence Between Communication Skills and Language Anxiety

Presented in Table 19 was the significant influence of the domains of communication skills that can considerably influence the language anxiety of BSED students. The results showed that competence, a domain of communication skills, appear to be a statistically significant predictor of the level of language anxiety of BSED education students, ($\beta = 0.521$, $p < .001$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the beta value indicates that for all units increase of competence, the level of language anxiety of BSED students will also increase by 0.521 units.

Also, the results showed that discouragement, a domain of communication skills, appear to be a statistically significant predictor of the level of language anxiety of BSED students, ($\beta = 0.143$, $p = .001$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Consequently, the beta value ($\beta = 0.143$) indicates that for every unit increase of discouragement, level of language anxiety will also increase by 0.143 units. Therefore, this leads to the rejection of the second null hypothesis states that there is/are a domains/s of communication skills that can significantly influence the language anxiety of the respondents.

Additionally, the results showed that body language, a domain of communication skills, appear to be a statistically significant predictor of the level of language anxiety of BSED students, ($\beta = -.178$, $p = .014$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, the negative beta value indicates that for all units decrease of body language, the level of language anxiety of BSED students will also decrease by -0.178 units.

Table 19. Significant Influence Between Communication Skills and Language Anxiety

Independent Variable Communication Skills	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P-value	Decision @=0.05
	β	SE	Beta			
(Constant)						
Competence	0.521	0.058	0.517	9.059	< .001	H ₀ Rejected
Discouragement	0.143	0.066		2.155	.031	H ₀ Rejected
Body Language	-0.178	0.072	-0.160	-2.480	.014	H ₀ Rejected
Dignification	0.270	0.072	0.227	3.777	< .001	H ₀ Rejected
Dependent Variable: Language Anxiety				Adjusted R square: .400		
F-ratio: 45.193						

Furthermore, the results indicated that dignification, a domain of communication skills, was a statistically significant predictor of the level of language anxiety among BSED students ($\beta = .270, p < .001$). At the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, the beta value suggests that for every unit increase in dignification, the level of language anxiety among BSED students would also increase by 0.270 units.

On the other hand, the p-values of the four domains did not exceed the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there was no domain that did not have a significant influence on language anxiety. Consequently, this suggests that all domains significantly influenced the language anxiety of the BSED students.

Moreover, communication skills explained a significant proportion of variance in BSED students' language anxiety, the $R^2=0.400, F=45.193$. The R^2 of 0.400 shows that the model predicts 40% of language anxiety is attributed to the influence of communication skills, while the coefficient of alienation which is 60% is due to unaccounted variables outside the study's scope. Consequently, the null hypothesis is not accepted.

Significant Influence Between Vocabulary Learning Strategies and Language Anxiety

Presented in Table 20 was the significant influence of the domains of vocabulary learning strategies towards the language anxiety of BSED students. The results showed that metacognitive strategy, a domain of vocabulary learning strategies, appear to be a statistically significant predictor of the level of language anxiety of BSED education students, ($\beta=0.249, p=.002$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the beta value indicates that for all units increase of metacognitive strategy, the level of language anxiety of BSED students will also increase by 0.521 units.

Table 20. Significant Influence Between Vocabulary Learning Strategies and Language Anxiety

Independent Variable Vocabulary Learning Strategies	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P-value	Decision @=0.05
	β	SE	Beta			
(Constant)						
Memory Strategy	0.071	0.075	0.068	0.950	.343	H ₀ Accepted
Cognitive Strategy	-0.093	0.067	-0.100	-1.396	.164	H ₀ Accepted
Metacognitive Strategy	0.249	0.078	0.270	3.193	.002	H ₀ Rejected
Determination Strategy	0.195	0.083	0.200	2.346	.020	H ₀ Rejected
Social Strategy	0.140	0.057	0.167	2.454	.015	H ₀ Rejected
Dependent Variable: Language Anxiety				Adjusted R square: .280		
F-ratio: 21.580						

Also, the results showed that determination strategy, a domain of vocabulary learning strategies, appear to be a statistically significant predictor of the level of language anxiety of BSED students, ($\beta=0.195, p=.020$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Consequently, the beta value ($\beta=0.195$) indicates that for every unit increase of determination strategy, level of language

anxiety will also increase by 0.195 units. Therefore, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis states that there is/are a domains/s of vocabulary learning strategies that can significantly influence the language anxiety of the respondents.

Additionally, the results showed that social strategy, a domain of vocabulary learning strategies, appear to be a statistically significant predictor of the level of language anxiety of BSED students, ($\beta=0.140$, $p=.015$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, the beta value indicates that for every unit of social strategy increase, the level of language anxiety of BSED students will also increases by 0.140 units. Therefore, metacognitive strategy, determination strategy and social strategy are the only indicators of vocabulary learning strategies that can significantly influence the language anxiety among Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students.

On the other hand, the other two remaining domains, memory strategy ($\beta=0.071$, $p=.343$) and cognitive strategy ($\beta=-0.093$, $p=.164$) do not have a significant influence on language anxiety. At 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of the two domains exceeded 0.05. This suggests that the memory strategy and cognitive strategy were not a significant predictor of language anxiety of the respondents. In memory strategy, the beta value ($\beta=0.071$) indicates that for every unit increase of memory strategy, level of language anxiety will also increase by 0.129 units.

Moreover, the p-value for the remaining domains, which is memory strategy ($\beta=0.071$, $p=.343$) appeared to be not statistically significant predictor of the language anxiety of the students. At the 0.05 level of significance, the p-values for the domains exceeded 0.05, suggesting that the memory strategy domain does not have a significant influence on the language anxiety of the students. The beta value ($\beta = 0.071$) indicates that for every unit increase in the use of memory strategy, the level of language anxiety would increase by 0.071 units. However, this implies that the memory strategy domain is unlikely to have any meaningful effect on the language anxiety of the students.

Also, the p-value for the remaining domains, which is cognitive strategy ($\beta=0.093$, $p=.164$) appear to be not statistically significant predictor of the language anxiety of the students. At 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of the domains exceeded 0.05. This suggest that the domain which is cognitive strategy do not have significant influence on language anxiety of the students. Prior to that, the beta value ($\beta=-0.093$) indicates that for every unit decrease of cognitive strategy, the level of language anxiety will also decrease by -0.093 units. This means that the domain is not likely to have any effect on the language anxiety of the students.

Furthermore, vocabulary learning strategies explained a significant proportion of variance in students' language anxiety, the $R^2=0.280$, $F= 21.580$. The R^2 of 0.280 shows that the model predicts 28% of language anxiety is attributed to the influence of communication skills, while the coefficient of alienation which is 72% is due to unaccounted variables outside the study's scope. Consequently, the null hypothesis is not accepted.

Conclusions

Drawing upon the results, conclusions were formulated in response to the questions posed in the preceding chapter. The respondents consistently reported a significant prevalence of communication skills, indicating that this variable is oftentimes observed by students.

Based on the result of communication skills as perceived by students, it was determined to be high. This means that the students often observe the presence of the variable. Moreover, based on the results regarding the vocabulary learning strategies of the students, it can be concluded that the level of vocabulary learning strategies among Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students was high. This indicates that the students frequently exhibited this variable. Additionally, when the students' level of language anxiety was assessed, it was determined to be moderate, suggesting that the language anxiety of the BSED students was sometimes manifested.

Furthermore, the correlation between communication skills and language anxiety revealed a significant relationship between the two variables. The study shows that social literacy has a moderate, positive, and significant relationship in to the language anxiety of the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

In addition, the correlation between the vocabulary learning strategies and language anxiety also revealed a significant relationship between the two variables.

The study also shows that vocabulary learning strategies has a moderate, positive, and significant relationship in to the language anxiety of the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Based on the result of regression analysis, in communication skills has four domains have shown significant influence to the communication skills. This means that the domains -- competence, discouragement, body language, and dignification -- are significant predictors of language anxiety of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 40% of the statistical variation with an $F= 45.193$ in the level of language anxiety of the respondents, while the remaining 60% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the language anxiety of the respondents.

Lastly, the regression analysis of vocabulary learning strategies has three domains that significantly influence the language anxiety of the respondents. This means that the domains -- metacognitive strategy, determination strategy and social strategy -- are significant

predictors of language anxiety. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 28% of the statistical variation with values of $F= 21.580$ in the level of language anxiety of the respondents, while the remaining 72% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the language anxiety of the respondents.

Among the indicators of communication skills, it was found that competence has the item with the lowest mean result. Hence, it is recommended that students do targeted activities to enhance their competence in communication skills. Engaging in public speaking workshops, participating in debates, and joining discussion groups can provide valuable practice and feedback. Additionally, incorporating regular practice of active listening exercises and role-playing scenarios can assist students in enhancing their non-verbal and verbal communication skills. These activities not only build confidence but also enhance the ability to articulate ideas clearly and effectively in various settings. By actively participating in these structured activities, students can significantly improve their communication competence, leading to better academic and professional outcomes.

Additionally, among the indicators of vocabulary learning strategies, it was determined that social strategy has the items with the lowest mean result. It is hereby recommended that these students will expose themselves in interacting with others and foster positive relationships with them such as group vocabulary games, peer teaching sessions, and language exchange programs. Classroom activities like vocabulary charades, collaborative storytelling, and word association games can make learning interactive and enjoyable, encouraging students to practice new words in social contexts. Organizing study groups where students discuss and quiz each other on vocabulary can also enhance their social learning strategies. Furthermore, implementing peer review sessions for writing assignments enables students to provide and receive feedback, fostering collaborative learning. By participating in these activities, students can strengthen their social strategies, which in turn enhances their vocabulary learning and overall language proficiency.

Moreover, among the indicators of language anxiety, it was found that fear of negative evaluation had the items with the lowest mean scored. It is hereby recommended that educators implement activities to create a supportive and non-judgmental classroom environment to lessen this fear. Activities such as peer-to-peer feedback sessions, where the focus is on constructive criticism and positive reinforcement, can help build students' confidence. Role-playing scenarios that simulate real-life communication situations allow students to practice without the pressure of being formally evaluated. Incorporating regular "praise rounds," where students highlight each other's strengths, can also foster a positive atmosphere. Additionally, using anonymous feedback methods, such as suggestion boxes or digital platforms, can provide students with a safe space to express their concerns and receive helpful feedback, ultimately reducing their anxiety about negative evaluations.

Overall, there is a high moderate and positive degree of correlation between communication skills and language anxiety of BSED students. It is hereby recommended educators provide resources and support to improve communication skills and thereby reduce language anxiety among students. Implementing regular practice sessions where students can engage in speaking activities, such as small group discussions or presentations, can help build confidence. Also, providing access to online language learning platforms and apps that offer interactive exercises and feedback can support independent learning.

Also, offering workshops on stress management and relaxation techniques, such as mindfulness and deep breathing exercises, can equip students with tools to manage anxiety. Additionally, creating a classroom culture that emphasizes positive reinforcement and celebrates progress, no matter how small, can significantly reduce students' fear of negative evaluation and encourage them to actively participate in communication activities.

Furthermore, there is a moderately positive correlation between vocabulary learning strategies and language anxiety among BSED college students. It is hereby recommended that educators provide accessible resources and support to improve students' vocabulary learning strategies and reduce language anxiety. Implementing vocabulary building apps and online tools that offer interactive exercises and games can make learning engaging and accessible outside the classroom. Furthermore, creating a supportive environment where students can share resources, ask questions, and discuss language learning challenges can foster collaboration and reduce anxiety. Encouraging regular self-assessment and reflection through daily journals can also help students monitor their progress and build confidence in their vocabulary learning journey. By integrating these accessible resources and support mechanisms, educators can help students enhance their vocabulary learning strategies while effectively managing language anxiety.

In conclusion, for the benefit of future researchers, a recommendation is made to consider employing a mixed-method approach when delving into the intricate interplay between communication skills, vocabulary learning strategies, and language anxiety. Although the present study centered on a quantitative research design involving 266 students, the utilization of a mixed-method approach holds promise for multiple reasons. The integration of quantitative data derived from surveys with qualitative insights obtained through interviews or focus groups stands to furnish a comprehensive panorama of students' perspectives and dispositions.

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